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Hybrid Simulation Platform

Eva Rodriguez, Liam Chen, Sofia Jensen

Max Planck Institute of Technology, Berlin, Germany; University of Technology, Sydney, Australia

ABSTRACT

This paper presents *ASSISI Playground*, a simulator for facilitating research in the area of collective bio-hybrid systems. Its development is motivated by the specific use-case of simulating bio-hybrid societies consisting of honeybees and static robotic units called CASUs (Combined Actuator-Sensor Units). However, due to its modular design, the simulator can easily be extended to other animal species and other types of robot. The distinguishing features of the software are the ability to simulate societies consisting of hundreds of individuals in real time, behaviour of individuals implemented in Python scripts that can be easily modified and extended by the user, and the ability to directly transfer controllers from simulated to real robots. Furthermore, the simulator implements several modalities of physical interaction that are not typically provided by conventional simulation frameworks but highly relevant to bio-hybrid research, including vibrations, airflow and heat transfer. In the paper, we describe the simulator architecture, provide implementation details for the physical interaction modalities and present two examples which demonstrate the usability of the simulator.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Nature abounds with examples of complex adaptive behaviours of large animal groups, which are produced by simple, repeated interactions between individuals. Examples of such behaviours include bird flocking, fish school migration, ant pheromone trail networks, termite mounds, cockroach aggregation and honeybee foraging. Even human crowds can exhibit such emergent behaviours. For decades, scientists have been working on identifying the underlying principles of *self-organization* (Sumpter 2006). The importance of understanding animal selforganization is twofold. Firstly, many of the animals exhibiting such behaviour have great economic importance. While swarms of locusts and ant colonies can inflict significant economic damage, our food supply depends on cattle herds and fish schools, as well as on colonies of honeybees and other pollinating insects, which are necessary for the production of 87 out of 115 leading global food crops (Klein et al. 2007). Secondly, the principles of self-organization can potentially be applicable to a wide variety of complex technical systems which consist of a large number of interacting units, such as the generation and distribution of electrical power or traffic networks. Ant colony optimization (Dorigo and Blum 2005) is one very successful example of a technical solution that has been inspired by collective animal behaviour.

Until recently, research on self-organization in collective animal systems has been largely limited to observation. The shortcoming of this methodology lies in the fact that the behaviour of individuals is dependent on the behaviour of their interaction partners. Until one is able to manipulate the behaviour of individuals, it can be difficult to obtain quantifiable results and verify scientific hypotheses. Fortunately, advances in robotics technology are enabling revolutionary new tools for the study of social behaviour in animals. Interactive robots can exhibit standardized behaviours, they enable the decoupling of morphology from behaviour, and can implement complex interaction sequences and embody behavioural models (Krause et al. 2011). Some research groups have already been successful in creating robots which have been accepted by animals as conspecifics (Halloy et al. 2007). Our project ASSISIBf (Animal and robot Societies Self-organise and Integrate by Social Interaction – bees and fish) aims to create mixed societies of honeybees and robots, as well as fish and robots, with a very high level of social integration. We have created specialized static robotic units, called CASU (Combined Actuator-Sensor Unit) (Griparic et al. 2015), capable of producing and sensing a variety of stimuli relevant for honeybee behaviour. By using multiple stimuli as communication channels, we hope to achieve effectively one single, integrated society, a *social cyborg* (Schmickl et al. 2013). We expect that such a bio-hybrid society can collectively perform tasks with greater efficiency and robustness than the individual biological and robotic societies.

Creating and experimenting with bio-hybrid societies is inherently a challenging and time-consuming task. In particular, researchers face the following specific challenges:

- Experimenting with animals is time consuming, and can be subject to seasonal constraints (e.g. honeybees are typically active only from late April until early September)
- Debugging algorithms on robotic hardware can be impractical and time consuming
- Solving some complex problems requires lengthy optimization procedures, such as evolutionary algorithms, which are impractical or impossible to run in an experimental setup with live animals

Computer simulation presents itself as a necessary tool for overcoming the difficulties mentioned above. End users require high-speed, qualitatively correct simulations of large numbers of individual entities, subject to a rich set of physical interactions. In addition to simple mechanical interaction (collision detection), research conducted within the ASSISIBf project requires modelling of heat diffusion, vibration propagation and air flow. Furthermore, the simulator should make it simple to implement and experiment with different behaviours of simulated entities. Transferring simulated behaviours to hardware devices should be possible without any code modifications. Due to the obvious importance of simulation tools in robotics and collective systems research, there is a wide variety of simulators available, either as commercial products or as open source projects. A detailed overview of the most popular simulators is provided by Staranowicz and Mariottini (2011). Two other interesting tools are NetLogo (Wilensky 1999), a programmable modeling environment for simulating natural and social phenomena, and ARGoS (Pinciroli et al. 2012), a simulator

specifically aimed at simulating multi-robot systems. However, none of the available tools were able to cover all of our requirements. In particular, we were not able to find a tool that can provide simple and efficient simulation of all stimuli relevant for honeybee interaction, such as heat and airflow, while at the same time providing the ability to run the same code in simulation and on hardware. Therefore, we have developed a novel tool, *ASSISI Playground*, that we describe in this paper. Our simulator is built on top of the Enki open source simulation engine (Magnenat et al. 2009).

In the following sections, we outline the simulator architecture, provide implementation details of the implemented physical modalities and present two illustrative examples of bio-hybrid society simulation.

2 SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

2.1 Simulator requirements

The primary motivation for the development of *ASSISI Playground* is providing a tool to support our research on bio-hybrid societies of bees and CASU devices within the ASSISibf project. Figure 1 shows our experimental setup. However,

Figure 1: Honeybees in the CASU array.

when designing the simulator, we have set ourselves a more ambitious design goal of providing a modular and extensible tool that can be useful in the general context of simulating collective bio-hybrid systems. Combining this overall design goal with our specific needs has yielded the following set of requirements:

1. Real-time simulation of large societies comprising hundreds of individuals
2. Scriptable behaviours of individuals
3. Calibrated models of different physical interactions: collisions, heat, vibration, airflow, object proximity
4. Transition from simulation to hardware without code modifications
5. High-speed headless simulation mode for tuning evolutionary algorithms

2.2 Simulator design

A high-level overview of the different system components is shown in Figure 2. The key design choice responsible for system modularity is the middleware layer built on

top of the ZeroMQ messaging protocol¹ and Protobuf message serialization². Using a messaging protocol enables the decoupling of the simulator engine from “controller code” which implements the behaviour of simulated entities. Sensor data and actuator commands are published through the middleware, and made available to the user through a Python API. This approach has been popularized in the robotics community by the ROS middleware (Quigley et al. 2009), and its advantages are twofold. Firstly, the user has full control over the behaviour of the simulated entities. For instance, different models of honeybee behaviour can be quickly implemented, tested and refined. Furthermore, because the simulated CASU devices use the same communication protocol as the real devices, code implementing CASU behaviour can be directly ported to hardware. This speeds up the development and debugging cycle significantly.

The simulation engine extends the Enki simulator (Magnenat et al. 2009) with additional physical modalities relevant for honeybee behaviour, as described in the following section.

3 PHYSICAL MODALITIES

In this section we describe the physical modalities that are currently implemented in the *ASSISI Playground*. Specifically, we have implemented heat, vibration and airflow physical modalities because of their responses in honeybees (see also Griparic et al. (2015) which describes the physical robot design).

3.1 Heat

The heat model is based on a Cellular Automaton (CA). Each cell represents a square area in the world, and so has a [variable] temperature. Heat flows from warmer cells to cooler cells, and can also directly flow to the outside world.

¹ <http://zeromq.org/>

² <https://developers.google.com/protocol-buffers/>

Figure 2: Software architecture overview.

Thermal flow only occurs between a cell and its Von Neumann neighbours. The update rule is:

$$h_i^{t+1} = \alpha \sum_{j \in N_i} h_j^t + (1 - \alpha) h_i^t + \alpha (H_W - h_i^t) D_W, \quad (1)$$

where h_i^t is the heat in cell i at time step t , N_i is the set containing the neighbouring cells of i , d_j is the thermal diffusivity of cell j , H_W is the outside temperature, D_W is the heat dissipation. The factor $(H_W - h_i^t) D_W$ represents heat flow to the outside world. Border cells are held at a temperature of H_W to model an infinite reservoir. This means that if there are no heat sources in the world, all cells will tend to H_W .

Parameter α depends on the cell size, and on time. When using bigger cells, the changes in temperature are slower. Temperature is updated at constant intervals. More specifically, Enki has a function responsible for updating the state of the world, which has a time step parameter (Δt). When this parameter is higher, more heat is transferred in one simulation time step. In order to avoid oscillations in equation (1), α cannot be greater than 1/4: larger values of α would result in Δh_i being bigger than the temperature difference between two adjacent cells. The value of α is:

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta t}{s^2}, \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Screenshot from the simulator with the heat visualization layer turned on. The layer is not completely opaque in order to show CASU positions.

where Δt is the simulation time step, and s is cell size.

3.1.1 Heat actuator

The heat actuators are characterised by a mesh of point sources with a thermal response time ζ . When a heat source is turned on, the cells where it is located start heating towards the target temperature. The equation used to compute the cell temperature is:

$$fH_T - (1 - f)h_i \quad (3)$$

where $f = \min(1.0, \zeta \Delta t)$ is a factor that depends on the thermal response time and the simulation time step Δt , and parameter H_T is the set temperature of the actuator.

A Combined Actuator-Sensor Unit (CASU) heat actuator is represented by a circumference of point sources. There are other types of point meshes available: circle and ring. The circumference mesh is has two parameters: radius and number of points. The points are equally spaced along the circumference, and, depending on the grid scale, each point may or may not correspond to a single cell. A fine grid scale increases realism but trades off with simulation cost (the computational effort decreases quadratically with increasing cell size).

3.1.2 Temperature sensor

A heat sensor is characterised by its location. It senses the temperature in the corresponding cell within the heat mesh.

Figure 3 shows a screenshot from the simulator with 25 CASUs, which are heating to target temperatures from the set $\{36, 38, 32, 34, 30, 28\}^\circ\text{C}$. The simulator visualisation is showing the heat layer. The CASU Peltier is made of copper and has a ring shape; accordingly, the corresponding cells have the thermal diffusivity of copper. Other cells have the thermal diffusivity of air. These different thermal diffusivity parameters, and the direct heat loss in cells, together mean that heat does not propagate so far from CASUs.

3.1.3 Heat model calibration

The model presented in this section has parameters that must be fine-tuned in order to correctly model a specific electronic device. We have run an experiment both in simulation and on the physical hardware, in which a single CASU

parameter	description	value
s	cell size	0.5cm
H_W	outside temperature	23°C
D_W	heat dissipation	10^{-6}
Δt	simulation time step	0.1
ζ	thermal response time	0.3
radius	radius of Peltier plate	1.6cm
numberPoints	number of points in circumference	

Table 1: Heat model parameters

periodically changes its set temperature in the sequence $\{42, 26, 38, 30, 34\}$ °C. Figure 4 shows the temperature measured in both setups. Table 1 provides the parameters that best match the data from a real CASU.

Figure 4: Comparison between temperature measured by a simulated and a real CASU. Both CASUs start by heating to 42°C, at $t = 120$ s they change to 26°C, at $t = 240$ s they change to 38°C, at $t = 360$ s they change to 30°C, and finally at $t = 480$ s they change to 34°C.

3.2 Proximity sensing

Phenomenologically, the bees are able to sense conspecifics and other objects in their environment at close proximity. We model this ability through infra-red proximity sensors. We use the implementation of infra-red sensors in Enki (Magnenat et al. 2009) as the underlying model of a proximity sensor. Table 2 shows the sensor model parameters. Note that each sensor has a height meaning that objects lower than this value are not perceived by the sensor. The sensor reading is based on an inverse square response function and three casted rays. Each ray is separated by an angle of 15 degrees. For each ray we compute a value given

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Table 2: Proximity sensor model parameters

parameter	description
pos	Relative position on the robot
height	Height above ground, the sensor will not see any object of smaller height
orientation	Relative orientation on the robot
rg	Actual detection range
aperture	Sensor aperture angle
α	Inverse of aperture
m	Maximum possible response value, might be inside the robot if $x_0 < 0$
x_0	Position of the maximum of response (might be negative, inside the robot)
c	Third parameter of response function
noiseSd	Standard deviation of Gaussian noise in the response space

by:

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x > \text{rg} \\ m & \text{if } x < x_0 \\ \frac{m(c - x_0^2)}{x^2 - 2x_0x + c} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where x is the distance from the sensor position to the nearest obstacle, and other parameters are described in table 2. The values of each ray are combined in order to produce:

$$G = F(d_c) + F(d_l) + F(d_r) - 2F(d_c \alpha) \quad (5)$$

where d_c , d_r , and d_l are the distance of centre, left and right rays, respectively, and $\alpha = 1/\cos(15^\circ)$. The sensor reading is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \text{rg} & \text{if } G = 0 \\ \min(\text{rg}, x_0/2) & \\ \square & \\ \text{if } G = m. & (6) \quad \left(\min\left(\text{rg}, x_0 + \sqrt{x_0^2 c(1 - m/G)}\right) \right) \\ \text{otherwise} & \end{cases}$$

If the result of the cast rays $F(x)$ is small, due to far away or undetectable objects, G will be small, and the sensor reading will be close to rg .

3.3 Vibration

Honeybees use vibrations within the nest to communicate (e.g., about the location of foraging sites, Michelsen et al. 1992).

The propagation of vibrations is modelled using the wave equation. This equation depends on time and space, and gives the wave amplitude s :

$$(7)$$

Table 3: Vibration actuator simulation model parameters

parameter	description
	quadratic decay
	maximum produced amplitude
	frequency
v	vibration speed, equal to speed of sound in copper
θ	phase
noise	frequency error

where x is the distance from the source, t is time, A is the maximum wave amplitude, f is the wave frequency, and v is the wave speed. This equation can be modified to consider damping.

3.3.1 Vibration actuator

We use a modification of equation (7) to model the vibration produced by a CASU. We assume that vibration travels in a 2 dimensional plane. x is the radial distance from the CASU vibration actuator, which is considered a point source.

In addition to equation (7), the vibration actuator is characterised by its phase θ and a frequency error. The phase allows multiple CASUs to vibrate at different phases, thus providing the possibility of vibrating out of sync. The frequency error is used when setting the frequency of a CASU. This models inaccuracy in real motors. When the user sets the frequency, the real frequency is set to the requested value plus a uniform noise with maximum value given by the frequency error. Given the variety of materials present in a CASU array, and their associated sound speeds, we assume that vibration travels at the maximum of these speeds (namely, the sound velocity in copper).

To account for decay, we assume that amplitude decays quadratically with distance. This is controlled by the rate parameter c . The equation that models the vibration produced by a CASU is:

(8)

Table 3 shows all parameters that control the vibration actuator's behaviour.

3.3.2 Vibration Sensors or Accelerometers

Vibration sensors measure the frequency and amplitude of all vibration actuators in the world. Both measures are perturbed by a Gaussian noise with average zero and a positive standard deviation. Vibration sensors return two vectors that correspond to the spectral response.

3.4 Airflow

Airflow is used to disrupt the bees and can be considered as a repulsive stimulus. Using this, CASUs may be able to steer bees away from specific areas.

3.4.1 Air Pump

An air pump is characterised by an orientation, an aperture angle, an intensity, and a range. This last parameter means that an object outside the air pump range does not sense any air flow. An air pump produces an air flow in a cone.

3.4.2 Air Sensor

An air sensor measures the air flow from all air pumps within range and within the aperture cone. Each air pump a contributes with an air flow intensity vector, \mathbf{i}_a . The sensed air flow is the sum of all contributing air pumps, $\sum_a \mathbf{i}_a$.

4 CASE STUDIES

4.1 Honeybee aggregation around heat source

Figure 5: Screenshot showing aggregation towards end of simulation. Bees aggregate at the warmer heat source. Bee colours indicate behavioural states (yellow=exploring; blue=avoiding object; red=paused, brighter red for longer pauses).

Figure 6: Bee location over time (upper) and statistically significant collective decision. For these parameters, it does not take long before the bees form a stable aggregation that contains most of the bees most of the time.

Juvenile honeybees form aggregations in warmer parts of their environment. It appears to be a social phenomenon: only with a sufficient population density do any aggregations arise. The strength of aggregation is modulated by the local environmental temperature, with the bees exhibiting a preference for 36°C.

To illustrate aggregation formation over time, we present a group of simulated animals with a binary choice between two heat sources, implemented by CASUs emitting a fixed temperature (see Fig. 5). One CASU is set to 36°C, the other at 28°C, and the ambient is set at 27°C.

Figure 7: CASUs employing their airflow actuators in an attempt to maintain the 50 bees in the central zone, where it is moderately attractive for them to be. The green overlay indicates non-zero airflow. Bee colours as per Fig. 5, and additionally white=agitated.

The bees use the individual-based model behaviour *Beeclust* (Schmickl et al. 2009), which has previously been demonstrated to capture the key features of the bee behaviour. In this model, the animals move randomly about the arena until they encounter a conspecific, at which time they stop for a period that depends on the local temperature. The closer to their preferred 36°C, the longer the pause. The specific implementation is described fully in Mills et al. (2015).

25 bees are initially placed centrally in the environment, and as they explore the arena and locate the warmer heat source, they begin to form an aggregation, which recruits the majority of the animals (Fig. 6, upper). We use a binomial test to formally quantify when the group has formed a significant decision at the collective level (see Halloy et al. 2007), which shows a stable aggregation is maintained after approximately 4 minutes (Fig. 6, lower).

Elsewhere we have shown that the model yields appropriate macro-level behaviour as a function of both heat source temperature and of bee group size (Mills et al. 2015). These responses are qualitatively similar to that observed in Szopek et al. (2013).

We are not presently able to quantitatively recreate results from the prior work due to the differences in heat sources used: here we use CASUs which do not generate the same temperature fields as prior equipment (most notably, the effect of each CASU is intentionally more localised). Calibration work for scenarios such as this is ongoing.

4.2 Affecting honeybee motion with airflow

In this illustration, we use the airflow actuators as a “virtual fence” (see, e.g., Butler et al. 2006), which will help to retain the bees within a central zone. There is a heat source in the centre, but this is insufficient to maintain an stable aggregation in this size arena (the expected time for a bee that leaves the aggregation to re-find it is a function of area to explore, which is significantly larger than in the previous case). Accordingly, the outer ring of CASUs attempt to help the bees remain nearby the inner CASU (see Fig. 7).

Since these simulations are progressing in parallel with the hardware implementation and lab testing cycle, we use this as an exploratory exercise. We use

Figure 8: Time course of bees retained inside the CASU ring, for different controller programs. Using airflow slows down the departure of bees, but ultimately does not prevent it. The dashed horizontal line indicates the expected fraction of bees inside, given a uniform distribution over the arena.

a minimal-assumptions extension to the *Beeclust* model as used above: when a bee senses airflow, it attempts to get away from the agitation by turning randomly and then moving forwards. The bees also have a “refractory” period that prevents being caught in an endless stressed state.

We use a simple controller for the ring of CASUs: when any of the inward-facing proximity sensors are triggered, the airflow is switched on temporarily; however this is overridden if any of the outward-facing sensors are triggered at the same time. The rationale is only to ‘erect the fence’ for bees on the inside, while letting bees on the outside back in. We compare this against two controls: 1) constantly emitting an airflow; and 2) actuators off (these still serve as a physical obstruction).

Although we might expect that an airflow with radius sufficient to be sensed entirely across a gap would offer an impermeable fence, this is in fact not the case. Neither the interactive robots nor the constant airflow robots are sufficient to maintain all of the bees within the central zone. However, when compared against the passive CASUs, the time it takes before the distribution of animals reaches approximately uniform over the whole arena (dashed horizontal line, Fig. 8) is increased.

This experiment illustrates how we can investigate experimental design and test predictions – and, in some instances, falsify them – before spending valuable laboratory time; instead, guiding us towards experiments that will offer higher chances of success.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have described a simulation tool aimed at supporting research of collective bio-hybrid systems. Although developed for the specific use case of honeybees and CASU devices, we believe *ASSISI Playground* can be a useful tool for research on other types of bio-hybrid systems. Its distinguishing features are the ability to simulate societies consisting of hundreds of individuals in real time, behaviour of individuals implemented in Python scripts that can be easily modified and extended by the user, and the ability to directly transfer controllers from simulated to real robots. The simulator also provides a rich set of physical interaction modalities: collision detection, heat transfer, infrared proximity detection, vibrations and airflow, which have been described in detail. Furthermore, we have presented the calibration of the heat transfer model against experimentally obtained data. Two simple usage examples

have been described, which involve CASU devices interacting with honeybees by modulating their individual and collective behaviour. The software is developed as an open source project, consisting of two separate modules: the simulator and the Python API. Both modules are publicly available on GitHub³⁴.

The simulator is being actively developed and several improvements are the subject of our ongoing work. As soon as experimental data becomes available, we will perform calibration of vibration and airflow modalities, using a methodology similar to the one we use for calibrating the heat model. We also plan to explore the limits of simulator scalability, i.e., find the maximum number of units that can be simulated in real time. A very important goal is to exploit headless simulation mode for running evolutionary algorithms. System parameters obtained in simulation by evolution will be experimentally evaluated on the bio-hybrid society of honeybees and CASU devices. Finally, we would like to see ASSISI Playground used for supporting research on other types of bio-hybrid societies.

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³ <https://github.com/larics/assisi-playground>

⁴ <https://github.com/larics/assisi-python>

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